

Renewable Energy Electrification Investment Prospect for Sizu Island, Tanzania

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

To achieve sustainable energy goals, renewable energy investment prospects coupled with an integrated Comprehensive Energy Planning Solution (CEPS) framework are vital for energy investment planning and implementation of the energy project under the localized energy need context.

The assessment involved a comparative analysis of various electrification scenarios, considering factors such as renewable energy integration and economic viability. MicrogridsPy was employed to model and simulate the performance of each scenario.

Scenario 1, which prioritizes a hybrid system comprising solar PV, battery storage, and generator technology, was identified as the most viable solution. This scenario offers a good balance between renewable energy utilization and economic viability.

The study highlights the importance of government interventions, including the development of a supportive policy framework, the establishment of financial incentives for renewable energy adoption, and the implementation of clear regulatory measures.

Further it underscores the importance of productive uses of electricity (PUE) to maximize the socio-economic benefits of electrification for the island's inhabitants.

1. BACKGROUND

Tanzania aims to significantly expand modern energy access in rural areas, aligning with Sustainable Development Goal 7 and its own SE4All Action Agenda. The country's targets, as outlined by (REA N. B., 2020)., include achieving 100% electricity access, 75% electricity connectivity, and 75% access to modern cooking solutions by 2030.

As of April 2025, Tanzania's electricity energy portfolio shows an overall access rate of 78.4%, with 99.6% in urban areas and 69.8% in rural areas. The generation mix is 2742 MW (68%) from renewables and 1290 MW (32%) from non-renewables. Electricity consumption demand is 1921 MW (as of April 2025). In the cooking sector, 89.7% of primary energy comes from biomass, with electricity accounting for only 3%.

The Government's investments in rural electrification through REA and TANESCO has increased the overall electricity access to all 12,318 villages; however under last mile reach electrification initiatives, off-grid RE solutions have proven to be effective and viable approach in providing electricity to isolated rural areas.

The Government's investments, channelled through REA and TANESCO, have resulted in increased electricity access across all 12,318 villages. However, off-grid renewable energy solutions have demonstrated their effectiveness and viability in delivering electricity to isolated areas (*through application of OnSSET model*), especially within last-mile reach electrification initiatives.

1. INTRODUCTION

Situated in Lake Victoria, Sizu Island is part of the Ukerewe district, Mwanza region, Tanzania. Its geographical coordinates are -1.93207, 33.05926. The island is home to around 2,300 residents, distributed across 453 households, with an average household size of 5 individuals. The island's economy is largely based on fishing, agriculture, and supplemented by welding and retail businesses.

Under last-mile reach electrification initiatives, effective electrification planning for a renewable energy-based microgrid is vital. Sizu Island was selected as a case study, and through CEPS (*Comprehensive Energy Planning Solution*) framework with the inclusion of RAMP and MicroGridsPy model, it enabled the establishment of the plant size, based on a Net Present Cost (NPC) optimized solution.

2. SCOPE

The study assessed renewable energy (RE) electrification investment prospects for Sizu Island using the CEPS framework. This involved developing scenarios and exploring between two distinct RE technology solutions to identify the least and optimal investment requirements.

3. OBJECTIVE

This study aims to determine the optimal renewable energy solutions for the sustainable electrification of Sizu Island and to develop an electrification plan that meets the island's energy needs and promotes its socio-economic development. in the context of country's broader electrification strategy and resource planning.

4. METHODOLOGY

This section outlines the methodology employed to assess and plan for the electrification of Sizu Island, utilizing the CEPS framework. The application of this framework provided a structured approach to evaluate various renewable energy system solutions and determine the optimal strategy for island-wide electrification.

The specific steps undertaken are detailed in the subsequent subsections, providing a clear and replicable process for achieving sustainable electrification. The first preliminary

three phases of the framework were used to assess RE electrification prospect for the selected case study. See Figure 1.

Figure 1. CESP Framework

4.1 Context Analysis

Under regulatory framework, the team showcased a set of existing regulatory framework which dictate and control renewable energy investment in Tanzania notably were: National Energy Policy (2003): National Environment Policy (2021): Electricity Act 2008 Cap 131: EWURA Act Cap 414: Mini grid Standards: SPPAs: Standardized Tariff Methodologies (STM) and Guidelines for Development of Small Power Projects (2011) which altogether acknowledge and set out procedure’s requirements for the RE investment¹. Summary procedural flow is outlined in **Figure 2**

Figure 2: Sequences of Implanting Small Power Producer (SPP)

¹ Procedures Outlines earmarked are crucial in identifying Government Regulatory Instruments and stakeholder mapping analysis i.e., Local Government Authority, EWURA, NEMC and Others.

Under Local Energy Need context, prior selection of investment type, through on field survey data, social- economic and demographic analysis for Sizu Island was carried to identify energy usage type in relation to energy needs. The summary profile is outlined in **Figure 3**.

Assessed Criterion	Data Description
1. Population Size	2300
2. Number of Household (HH)	453
3. Average Persons per HH	5
4. Public Institution(s)	1-Dispensary, 1-Primary School & 1-Village Office
6. Private Institutions(s)	1-Church, 1-Mosque
7. Social Economic Activities	In Total 20: Fishing/Sardine Vendor (4): Food Vendor (4): Retail Shops (4): Video Showroom (1): Local Bar (1): Barbershop (2) Welding Services (2): Maze Milling machine (2)

Figure 3. Socio-economic and demographic profile for Sizu Island

4.2 Resources and Demand Assessment

Effective electrification planning for Sizu Island hinges on a comprehensive understanding of its present energy resources and future demand. While the island possesses significant biomass potential, solar photovoltaic (PV) technology has demonstrated greater effectiveness in terms of technological maturity, operability, reliability, and sustainability. Sizu Island benefits from a Global Horizontal Irradiance (GHI) of 2123.8 kWh/m² per year, further supporting the viability of solar PV solutions. The average daily profile for Sizu Island is presented in **Figure 4**.

Figure 4. The average daily profile for Sizu Island

To assess energy demand, a survey was conducted to establish energy usage categories, appliances, and trends. Based on the socio-economic and demographic analysis detailed in Section 4.1, a total of 15 Energy User Categories were defined. The demand survey data is provided in **Annex I**.

These data were then used as inputs for the RAMP tool, an open-source software suite for the stochastic simulation of user-driven energy demand time series, to formulate a

demand profile. A one-year stochastic analysis of the demand data was modelled, and the aggregated demand formulation for the 15 user categories is presented in **Figure 5**.

Figure 5. Average Daily Hourly Load Profile

Peak load occurs daily between 15:00 and 18:00, driven by high demand from user categories involved in socio-economic activities, including milling machine services, welding machines, local bars, video showrooms, and fish vendors.

Between 18:00 and 23:00, the load decreases due to the cessation of high-demand socio-economic activities, with low demand usage limited to lighting across all 15 user categories.

A low demand period is evident from 5:00 to 6:00, with only outdoor lighting active across all 15 energy user categories. A medium-low demand period occurs from 1:00 to 4:00, characterized by outdoor lighting and operational freezers (for fish/sardine storage) within the Fish/Sardine User Category.

4.3 Technical Design

Sizing of the technological solution for electrification of Sizu island under CEPS framework require a set of pre-defined data generated from the RAMP tool and other specific location-based data. Additionally, the sizing modelling also took into account a set of assumptions to characterize a set of data or a thought scenario of an area.

The sizing of the electrification solution for Sizu Island, within the CEPS framework, relies on a set of pre-defined data from the RAMP tool and other location-specific information. Additionally, the sizing model incorporates assumptions to characterize a set of data or a thought scenario of an area.

4.3.1 Data Source

Under an explorative approach, the team used a series of available load demand survey data/report and energy resource potential data from open-source energy

data information platforms such as energydata.info, the Global Wind, Solar Atlas, Renewable Ninja and others as input data to RAMP and MicroGridsPy model tools.

4.3.2 Assumptions and Scenarios Approach

Prior to utilizing the MicroGridsPy tool for generation plant sizing on Sizu Island, several key assumptions were necessary to establish a clear and consistent modelling framework:

1. Data from the Power System Master Plan (PSMP, 2020) projections provided the annual power demand growth rates for a five-year period. Based on this, demand growth was modelled over the period, assuming no change in customer appliance usage behaviour. The resulting daily hourly demand growth profile over the five years is illustrated in **Figure 6**.

Figure 6. Daily Hourly Demand Growth

2. To develop aspirational scenarios, the team created two distinct scenarios, each with unique in-model assumptions based on technological energy solutions. **Figure 7** summarizes the scenario descriptions and assumptions. Scenario 1 was designed to reflect current rural electrification initiatives under Result Based Financing (RBF) Program.

Scenario Label	RE Technology	Grid Connection	Fuel Cost	Battery Type	Capacity Expansion	Infrastructure Type	Optimization Type	Renewable Penetration
Scenario 1	Solar PV + Battery + Generator	No	Variable Cost	Lithium Ion	No	Greenfield	Single Objective	75%
Scenario 2	Solar PV + Battery	No	None	Lithium Ion	No	Greenfield	Single Objective	100%

Figure 7: Scenario Descriptions and in model assumptions

5. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

The following results highlight investment trends, including capital requirements and electrification approaches, and outline the necessary technological composition for electrifying Sizu Island. The results and their implications are presented below.

5.1 Investment Implication

Net present cost (NPC) and Levelized Cost of Energy (LCOE) under both modelled scenarios results is as shown below by **Figure 8**.

Cost Item	Scenario 1	Scenario 2
NPC (kUSD)	271.26	898.2
LCOE (USD/kWh)	0.3332	1.12

Figure 8. NPC & LCOE Scenarios Comparison

Scenario 1, which utilizes solar PV, battery, and generator technologies, presents the most optimized electrification solution for Sizu Island. Its Net Present Cost (NPC) of 271.26 kUSD is significantly lower than the 898.2 NPC of Scenario 2, which relies solely on solar PV and battery technology

Despite Scenario 1 having the lowest LCOE, still government interventions play a crucial role in making LCOE competitive for RE investments due to its positive attribute in affecting tariff setup for widespread adoption for sustainable electricity use.

Effective policy frameworks, strategic planning, and financial incentives can significantly reduce the perceived and actual costs of renewable energy, driving investment and deployment.

Furthermore, these interventions are essential in promoting productive uses of electricity (PUE) that stimulate socio-economic activities, creating new opportunities and enhancing livelihoods.

5.2 Cost Breakdown

The cost breakdown analysis for each scenario developed for Sizu Island's electrification, as modelled by MicrogridsPy, yielded the following results for scenarios 1 and 2, respectively, see **Figure 9, 10 & 11**

Cost Item	Scenario 1	Scenario 2
	Value (kUSD)	Value (kUSD)
Total Investment Cost (Actualized)	251.53	1185.12
Total Variable Cost (Actualized)	113.52	136.27
Total Fixed O&M Cost (Actualized)	22.96	96.11
Total Battery Replacement Cost (Actualized)	20.79	40.16
Total Fuel Cost (Actualized)	69.77	0
Total Salvage Value (Actualized)	93.79	423.19

Figure 9. Cost breakdown between Scenarios

Figure 10. Cost Breakdown Comparison

Scenario 1

Scenario 2

Figure 11. Percentage Cost Contribution Breakdown

Despite **Scenario 2** being environmentally sustainable (Zero Emission), the trade-off advantage of generator in **Scenario 1** is in adding a layer of reliability and the ability to handle high power demands that a solar PV and battery system alone might struggle with especially during wet seasons. Underscoring ability in:

- **Meeting Peak Demand:** High load demands often occur in short bursts (e.g., when many people use appliances simultaneously). A generator can quickly provide the extra power needed during these peaks, preventing blackouts or brownouts. Batteries might not be able to discharge power fast enough to meet these sudden surges.
- **Ensuring Continuous Supply:** In situations where the load demand is consistently high over extended periods, a generator can supplement the solar and batteries, ensuring a continuous power supply. This is particularly important for critical infrastructure like health and economic productive sectors.
- **Bridging the Gap:** A generator can act as a bridge during extended periods of low solar generation, such as prolonged cloudy weather or long nights. This prevents the batteries from being completely drained and ensures that power is always available.
- **Cost Optimization:** For very high demand scenarios, relying solely on solar and batteries would require a massive investment in both solar panel arrays and very large battery banks as observed in **Section 5.2**.

5.3 Plant Size

This section presents the findings of the plant sizing analysis for the electrification of Sizu Island, derived from the application of the MicrogridsPy tool. The results detail the optimal capacity of each technology component under two defined scenarios. The selected optimal size for Sizu island electrification is **scenario 1**. See **Figure 12**.

RE Technology	Scenario 1	Scenario 2
Solar PV (kW)	115	179
Battery (kWh)	218	2175
Diesel Generator	27	0

Figure 12. System Sizing

5.4 Load Demand

The yearly load demand profile modelled under each scenario was based on analysing two separate period of the year 1 and year 5 for dry and rainy season respectively. Average energy balance and usage by technology under each scenario are presented in **Figure 13 & 14**.

Figure 13. Scenario 1 & 2: Energy Balance Profile

Figure 14: Average Energy Usage by Technology

The implicative results provide an insightful review on electricity production and usage trends along Sizu Island, concluding that the results imply that;

For scenarios 1 & 2, dry season (Year 1 & 5), the energy balance profile indicates that there is a surplus amount of energy generated by Solar PV as curtailment amount, and mostly the generator usage is at a minimum.

Leveraging potential surplus energy requires the deployment of two key strategies: demand-side management through tariff optimization, and advocating for the promotion of Productive Use of Electricity (PUE) activities.

During the rainy season, when solar energy intensity is minimal and Scenario 1 relies heavily on the generator for energy balance, a smart control integrated system should be incorporated to effectively optimize generator operational performance.

6. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the analysis conducted using the MicrogridsPy tool under the CEPS framework indicates that Scenario 1 presents a viable approach for the electrification of Sizu Island. The optimized combination of solar PV, battery storage, and generator technology within this scenario offers a cost-effective and reliable solution for meeting the island's energy needs. While ongoing monitoring and potential adjustments may be necessary, the results suggest that Scenario 1 can effectively balance renewable energy integration with the need for a stable and consistent power supply, paving the way for sustainable development on Sizu Island.

6.1 Recap and lessons learnt

This analysis focused on utilizing the MicroGridsPy energy model within a Comprehensive Energy Planning Solution (CEPS) framework to determine the financial resource requirements for a renewable energy-based electrification solution for Sizu Island.

In-training experience drawn from analysis made under the selected case study has highlighted the key lessons learned:

- I. **The Importance of Integrated Planning:** The CEPS framework highlighted the necessity of integrating technical modeling (MicroGridsPy) with broader socio-economic and financial planning. This ensures that the electrification project is not only technically feasible but also financially viable and socially acceptable.
- II. **Data Accuracy is Crucial:** The accuracy of the MicroGridsPy model's outputs is highly dependent on the quality of input data, including load profiles, renewable energy resource availability, and technology costs. Detailed and reliable data collection is essential for effective planning.
- III. **Renewable Energy Potential:** The study demonstrated the significant potential of renewable energy sources for island electrification. MicroGridsPy played a vital role in identifying the optimal mix of renewable technologies, reducing dependence on conventional fuels and promoting environmental sustainability.
- IV. **Financial Viability:** Assessing the financial requirements of the electrification project is critical for securing funding and ensuring long-term sustainability. The CEPS framework provided a valuable tool for this assessment, enabling policymakers and investors to make informed decisions.
- V. **Community Engagement:** While not explicitly detailed, the success of any electrification project, particularly in remote island communities, hinges on community engagement. Future applications of this approach should emphasize the active participation of local residents in all stages of project planning and implementation.
- VI. **Scalability and Replicability:** The approach of combining MicroGridsPy with a comprehensive planning framework can be scaled and replicated to other island communities or remote areas facing similar electrification challenges.

6.2 Recommendations

Tanzania aims to achieve an annual electricity consumption of 490 kWh per capita by 2025, a benchmark indicative of middle-income countries (REA, 2020). To meet this target, localized energy investment planning using the CEPS framework is essential for assessing the financial and technological resource requirements of isolated rural areas.

Further to actualize the optimization of the MicroGridsPy tool, the tool should provide a direct or indirect extension to network planning tool(s). This is essential for the designing optimization of the plant size in relation to loss accounted factors and dispersion nature of localities within the targeted areas.

6.4 Future Work

Future work should focus on developing and implementing strategies to effectively utilize surplus energy. This includes conducting in-depth research on dynamic tariff optimization models that incentivize demand-side management, and creating pilot programs to demonstrate the economic and social benefits of promoting Productive Use of Electricity (PUE) activities

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Annex I- Demand Survey Data

Sn.	User Category	Number of Users	Appliances	Number of App.	Power Rating
1	high income	93	HI_Outdoor Lighting	4	5
			HI_Indoor Lighting	4	3
			HI_Radio	1	15
			HI_Phone_charger	3	5
			HI_TV	1	50
2	low income	360	LI_Outdoor Lighting	2	5
			LI_Indoor Lighting	2	3
			LI_Radio	1	15
			LI_Phone_charger	3	5
			LI_Fridge	1	350
3	Dispensary	1	D_Outdoor Lighting	4	5
			D_Indoor Lighting	5	3
			D_Radio	1	15
			D_Phone_charger	4	5
			D_TV	1	50
			D_Freezer	1	350
4	Primary School	1	S_Outdoor Lighting	24	5
			S_Indoor Lighting	28	3
			S_Radio	2	15
			S_Phone_charger	18	5
			S_TV	2	50
			S_Printer	1	300
			S_PC	1	50
5	Village Office	1	VO_Outdoor Lighting	2	5
			VO_Indoor Lighting	2	3
6	church	1	Ch_indoor_bulb	4	3
			Ch_outdoor_bulb	4	5
			Ch_speaker	1	1000
			Ch_Phone_Charger	2	5
7	Mosquo	1	Mo_indoor_bulb	4	3
			Mo_outdoor_bulb	4	5
			Mo_speaker	1	1000
			Mo_Phone_Charger	2	5
8	Milling Machines	2	MM_Outdoor Lighting	2	5
			MM_Indoor Lighting	1	3
			MM_Phone_charger	2	5
			MM_Radio	1	15
			MM_Machine	1	7000
9	Welding Machines	2	WM_Outdoor Lighting	2	5
			WM_Indoor Lighting	1	3
			WM_Phone_charger	2	5
			WM_Radio	1	15
			WM_Glender	1	800
10	Barbershop	2	B_Outdoor Lighting	1	5
			B_Indoor Lighting	1	3
			B_Phone_charger	2	5
			B_Speaker	1	500
			B_Machine	2	15
11	Video Showrooms	1	VS_Outdoor Lighting	1	5
			VS_Indoor Lighting	1	3
			VS_Speaker	1	500
			VS_Phone_charger	2	5
			VS_TV	1	50
12	Local bar	1	LB_Outdoor Lighting	2	5
			LB_Indoor Lighting	4	3
			LB_Speaker	2	600
			LB_Phone_charger	4	5
			LB_TV	1	50
			LB_Fridge	1	350
13	Retail shops	4	RS_Outdoor Lighting	1	5
			RS_Indoor Lighting	1	3
			RS_Radio	1	15
			RS_Phone_charger	2	5
			RS_Fridge	1	350
14	Food vendor_Kiosk	4	FV_Outdoor Lighting	1	5
			FV_Indoor Lighting	1	3
			FV_Radio	1	15
			FV_Phone_charger	2	5
15	Fish/Saldin_vendor	4	FSV_Outdoor Lighting	1	5
			FSV_Indoor Lighting	1	3
			FSV_Radio	1	15
			FSV_Phone_charger	2	5
			FSV_Freezer	8	600

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